

RELEVANCE OF SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION TO NIGERIAN SOCIETY IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with how Social Studies Education affects people's behaviour in the society. The Nigerian educational aims and goals are developed to achieve its national objectives. To achieve these objectives, Social Studies is taught right from the primary school to the Junior Secondary school level. As a teacher of this subject, some recommendations are made. Among them is the extension of Social Studies Education to the Senior Secondary School Level.

Keywords: *Social Studies, Education, Nigerian Society*

Introduction

Man as a social being lives in a physical environment. He settles on land areas and makes use of everything at his disposal. The necessity to survive makes him see the essence of living in an organized and orderly society. Members of the society have to be trained and groomed to function by developing abilities for social responsibilities. Social Studies as a problem solver is saddled with the responsibility of training everybody to become useful and functional members of the society (Ogundare, 2003). It is a problem solver because the content of programmes of studies are based on the needs which are defined by the society itself. Social Studies programme changes as the society changes. It inculcates in the students the knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and actions considered important concerning the

relationship of human beings and their environment.

Education is worldly recognized as an instrument that can be used to achieve technological and national development. This is why the Federal Government of Nigeria declared in the National Policy on Education that "education is an instrument par excellence for effecting national development" (FRN, 2004) To address issues militating against the growth and development of the educational system, government in the past packaged different programmes to reform education. Some examples of educational reforms are the abolition of sixth form classes and the change in duration of secondary education from five years to six years, the inclusion of the first three years of secondary education (Junior Secondary School Level) into the basic education scheme which was the 6-3-3-4 system. Now the minimum qualification for teaching in a Senior Secondary School is the first degree with the teacher's qualification. Surprisingly, these reform efforts notwithstanding, the level of moral decadence appears to be on the increase in schools and the standard of education is seriously declining everyday.

There comes the thought provoking question, what has the teaching of Religious Knowledge achieved in schools? It is overwhelming to note the level of acts of indiscipline and moral decadence that has befallen Nigerian education sector. This sector is a haven of negative values such as examination malpractice, riot/demonstration, illicit sexual activities, drug-abuse, truancy, stealing, cultism and indecent dressing. To address these problems, Ogundare (2003) opined that the Department of Social Studies of Aiyetoro Comprehensive High School prepared the first Social Studies programme for secondary school students between 1964 and 1966. The introduction of Social Studies in schools was to solve the political, economic and social problems in Nigeria. It was their belief that Social Studies will help to achieve unity in Nigeria, make the Nigerians' ways of life known to students, make individual community to be conscious of others' existence

and therefore develop the spirit of self-sacrifice and self-reliance.

Many states in Nigeria accepted the teaching of Social Studies up to 1982. This was because the Federal government proposed that as from 1982, when the first batch of Universal Primary Education (UPE) Scheme would be graduating, secondary education would be six years duration offered in 3-3 sequences to give effect to the 1977 National Policy on Education. In 1985, the Federal government harmonized the existing subjects curricular and came up with the National Curriculum for Junior Secondary Schools. The objectives indicated what the students should be able to do after the completion of the topics. Ogundare (2003), asserted that the programme was designed along themes that they considered to be of vital interest to the nation and comprehensive to the students. In recent times this programme had been slightly modified by different states of the nation to suit their peculiarities; but by and large, the 1985 National curriculum can still be said to be the subsisting National programme up till date.

Nature of Social Studies

Every school subject has its basic structure, materials and functions. There are techniques of understanding its essence and what to learn from day-to-day. Social Studies is quite different from other traditional subjects like History, Geography, Religious Knowledge, to mention just a few. The uniqueness of it is found in the type of knowledge contained in the subject and the purpose of teaching it. This subject is to be taught in schools to curb the social vices in the society and to inculcate in students the right values necessary for peaceful co-existence. To this effect, the paper views the teaching of Social Studies in schools as one of the ways to achieve the Nigerian Educational goals as stated in the National Policy on Education.

No single definition of Social Studies has been accepted globally. There are as many definitions as the number of people giving them. In Nigeria what

we view as Social Studies is different from what America sees as the subject. However, there is a general consensus that man is the focus with the basic purpose of teaching Social Studies to prepare students for social responsibilities and perpetuate the good heritage and integrity of one's own society.

Kissock (1981), defined Social Studies as a programme of study which a society uses to instill in students the knowledge, skills, attitudes and actions it considers important in the relationship human beings have with each other, their work and themselves. The Nigerian Educational Research Council (1981), opined that Social Studies is the learning of man's interaction with his social and physical environment. This means that the subject studies man in all ramifications. The physical environment consists of his climate, dry land, rivers, thick forest, highlands and lowlands. The distribution of rainfall determines what man produces on his farms. Man has the will to move from one environment to another if he is not pleased with where he is. The social environment includes how man lives, his religion, his government and how individuals are trained for acceptance in the society. According to Ogundáre (2003), Social Studies is the study of problems of survival in an environment and how to find solutions to them. From this definition, man can change his environment with the knowledge of Science and Technology. For example, we dig well to get water and dig the ground to get crude oil. All of these show the relevance of Social Studies in the School Curriculum.

According to Makinde (1979), the initial aims of teaching Social Studies were:

- 1) To make Nigerian students understand their environment and their relationships with the physical, economic, social, cultural environment. This is quite relevant to the Nigerian society because without a clear knowledge of one's environment, no development can take place. This knowledge helps the society to plan and make effective use of both their physical and social

environment. A farmer studies the weather to know what to plant, where best to plant, and when to plant for bountiful harvest. Different cultures are studied and at times imbibed, thus bringing about cross-cultural ideas and philosophies. Being involved in economic activities within the society brings about national growth and development. All of these help to teach tolerance and accommodations of different tribes or cultures.

2) To make students know that all subjects are related and are just like branches of a tree with a common stem. Social Studies drew its contents from the Social sciences like Geography, Anthropology, Philosophy, History, Economics, Psychology and others. The general knowledge of these subjects are brought into Social Studies Education which becomes clearer and visible. Social studies is not taught in isolation but rather an inter-disciplinary subject. It emphasized a fusion of different disciplines and the contents provide background knowledge which enables students build on the already existing foundations.

3) To help teachers and pupils to discover what is good and unique in the physical, social, economic and cultural traditions. Teachers cannot give what they do not have. They must be well equipped with what to disseminate to their students. The knowledge of their subject matter will help to discover the different cultures and the individual differences in their students so as to know the right assistance to give to them.

4) To develop, encourage and strengthen enquiry minds in students. This will help them to re-discover what has been neglected or forgotten. Students of Social Studies are taught to discover their talents. This education is to be used to meet the needs of individuals for vocational and industrial competence needed for human survival.

Bearing the above aims in mind, it can be deduced that Social Studies Education is meant to integrate the society to be sound and effective citizens who are able to function efficiently in the societies they belong. The teaching

of Citizenship Education and patriotism produce good character and moral training needed for national unity in Nigeria. Students in the course of acquiring Social Studies Education are taught the right values that should be eschewed. Stealing, drunkenness, examination malpractice, riot and other deviant behaviours are discouraged in Social Studies Education.

The Social Studies Curriculum

Curriculum as a concept has many definitions: Mezieobi (1993), asserted that curriculum is planned or unplanned societally approved educational experiences which the learners are provided with and exposed to in and outside the school for the accomplishment of specified educational objectives. While Taba (1962) opined that, a curriculum is a documented plan for learning or the provision of learning opportunities geared towards the accomplishment of set educational goals. Social Studies Curriculum therefore, is all planned and unplanned learning activities, experiences, contents and instructional activities, given to learners at school and outside the school by the teachers so as to achieve specific educational objectives.

The integrative emphasis in Social Studies is to allow students view the social world and the problems as a whole and not as unplanned body of knowledge. The sources of Social Studies Curriculum contents are from the learner, the society, the knowledge, and learning experiences of the learners. No functional curriculum is used without references to the society. The society is an important source of Social Studies Curriculum. There needs to be the provision for incorporation into the curriculum the societal ways and aspirations with due attention to the multi-cultural and ethnic differences. The study and identification of societal realities entail a critical societal needs analysis. This analysis will help to teach students what is needed in the society.

The learner is also a source of Social Studies curriculum. Social Studies curriculum is child centred because the wants, interests, abilities, socio-economic backgrounds and individual differences of learners are put into consideration. What the child needs to learn and grow with are considered in planning a Social Studies Curriculum. The knowledge of the different stages of children's growth guides the selection of content for the Social Studies curriculum.

The knowledge and learning experiences of the learners is also a source of Social Studies Curriculum. The contents of Social Studies have been enlarged to include Hygiene, Nature studies and Environmental Studies. Different subjects like: Government, History, Literature, Economics, Biology and Languages are some of the disciplines from which Social Studies contents are drawn. In planning Social Studies Curriculum, decisions have to be taken on the different aspects of the wide spectrum of knowledge to be included. A careful selection should be made so as to meet the societal needs and aspirations at specific times. We have the following topics in the Social Studies Syllabus at Junior Secondary School:

- 1) Social organization.
- 2) Attitude to work.
- 3) Natural resources.
- 4) Institutions like marriage, health & religion
- 5) Culture and identity
- 6) Leadership and Followership
- 7) Political, Economic, Social Development in Nigeria
- 8) Concepts of Science and Technology
- 9) The Uniqueness Universality of Man
- 10) Inter-community Relation.

These topics are taught in schools to provide needed informal skills and

relevant information which will help to shapen the future of students. Social Studies is meant to train students in the skills of formulating and directing useful ideas that will promote growth and development in the country. Social Studies Education in schools integrates groups. When values like patience tolerance and respect for laws and order are inculcated in students, there will be unity and progress in the society.

Conclusion

The teaching of Social Studies is meant to help students acquire relevant knowledge which is an essential pre-requisite to personal development as well as to contribute to the development of their environment and the world at large. This means that much still has to be done in Social Studies, for the aims to be maximally achieved.

Considering the year the subject was introduced, one would expect a decline in the number of students' involved in deviant behaviours in schools but the increase is quite alarming. Students now perfect their criminal activities because they are in a technological age. It is noted with dismay that instead of youths to imbibe worthwhile values, they imbibe things that would hinder development in the society. Some of these vices are examination malpractice, thuggery, stealing, drug addition, violence and illicit sexual activities. These acts will not promote peaceful co-existence and where there is no peace, there cannot be development. Many students are involved in examination malpractice in the Junior Secondary School Examination while some are in the act of stealing at home and in the school. The teaching of Social Studies in schools is very adequate and definitely necessary. For more effectiveness, efforts should be doubled by teachers, parents and the government. Concerted and adequate commitment on the part of everybody in the society will go a long way to achieve Social Studies objectives.

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Recommendations

For more effectiveness, it is recommended that the teaching of Social Studies should not terminate at the Junior Secondary School Classes. It should be extended to the Senior Secondary School Classes. In the Senior Secondary classes, maturity is greater and students must have acquired more experiences of life more than what they have acquired in the Junior classes.

There should be more conducive learning environment where adequate instructional materials would be provided. Necessary infrastructures like classrooms, library, electrical gadgets like video tapes and television provided by the government. All of these materials would aid teaching and make learning more permanent because they can see, touch and feel when necessary.

At home, right values should be taught by parents and adults in the society at large. The society should eschew values by encouraging and promoting virtuous living. Acts that are not conforming with societal standards like stealing, indecent dressing, lack of respect, etc should be condemned and punished appropriately. Social Studies teachers should live by example. They should be role models that can be copied by the students they teach.

harmony and social developments are lacking. Nigeria is a multi-religious, multi-ethnic nation and has been having its fair share in the distractions that come with its colouration. This is not to say that a multi-religious nation cannot progress, but a lot depends on the understanding and management of these differences as driven by political leaders.

Christianity has a great role to play on peaceful co-existence in Nigeria. Christianity is on the side of justice and peace, it has a great role to play in building peace among the citizenry. Christianity, as a religion, holds great

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